

Engage_IoT

Engagements with the Internet of Things

REPORT 2 MEDIA ANALYSIS: IOT REPRESENTATIONS

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Summary

[Engage IoT](#) is a research project funded by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (EXPL/SOC-SOC/1375/2021). The core aim of this project is to understand how social actors (producers, consumers, regulators) engage with a new kind of technology (IoT), from the macro level of sociotechnical imaginaries to the micro level of practices of use.

This report summarises the quantitative analysis of news articles about IoT in three newspapers: Público (Portugal), El País (Spain) and The Guardian (UK). Overall, media coverage of the topic is not very frequent and has been declining in the past few years. A significant proportion of articles are short new articles and IoT is seldom the main topic of the article. Companies are the most frequently mentioned social actors in news articles. Focus on domestic applications of IoT is more frequent in The Guardian articles, with a wider diversity of IoT appliances mentioned. Positive articles about IoT are more frequently found in El País, negative ones in The Guardian, though most articles tend to be either neutral or balanced. Concurrently, risks are more often mentioned in The Guardian articles and benefits in El País.

Introduction

The core aim of this project is to understand how social actors (producers, consumers, regulators) engage with a new kind of technology (IoT), from the macro level of sociotechnical imaginaries to the micro level of practices of use.

Sociotechnical imaginaries are ‘imagined forms of social life and social order that centre on the development and fulfilment of innovative scientific and/or technological projects.’ (Jasanoff & Kim 2009: 120). These imaginaries are visions of the future collectively held and institutionally stabilized. According to Mager & Katzenbach (2020: 225), they are ‘a popular analytical tool to describe and understand the coproduction of technoscientific projects, social constellations and politics. It serves as a lens through which the interplay and mutual shaping of science, technology and society can be identified and analysed’ (Mager & Katzenbach 2020). In its original sense, it focused on the discourses and practices of governmental actors and public institutions. Later, through the work of other academics, was expanded to include the visions of companies, civil society, research communities and other organized groups (Mager & Katzenbach 2020).

With regard to sociotechnical imaginaries, this project proposed to tackle the following questions:

- How is IoT envisioned by policy-makers, regulators, innovators (scientist), business companies (that manufacture and market these devices), architects and engineers (who incorporate these devices in homes), civil society organisations (consumer associations, digital rights interest groups) and citizens? How is it defined, constructed, and contested? What narratives and imaginaries about the present and the future are mobilised?
- What are the perceived affordances, benefits and impacts over the economy and society of this technology? How does this perception vary among social actors?
- What are the perceived risks of IoT in these sociotechnical imaginaries? How are they assessed, anticipated, measured, mitigated? How are social and ethical concerns taken in consideration? What legal and ethical safeguards are put in place?
- How are technological developments in IoT regulated, incentivised or constrained by supranational and national policy making bodies? Which considerations affect policy decision, legislation and R&D funding practices? How do different types of knowledge are taken in consideration and which governance mechanisms are put in place?
- What dialogue or rapports are established between policy makers, business companies, scientists, architects and engineers, stakeholders and the public with regard to IoT?

- Which concerns, needs, interests are expressed by citizens/consumers regarding IoT? How is information obtained and understood? How does trust and mistrust affects adoption, attitudes and practices towards this technology?

To characterise the sociotechnical imaginaries of IoT several empirical approaches were implemented: document and media analysis, interviews with stakeholders. This report is based on an analysis of IoT representations in press articles from three European newspapers (online editions): The Guardian (UK), El País (Spain) and Público (Portugal). These newspapers were chosen because they are daily quality newspapers, that cover technology issues and two of them have an international readership (El País in Spanish speaking countries, The Guardian in English speaking countries). A search on the search engine provided by the websites, using the keyword “Internet of Things” (and its translation in Spanish and Portuguese), between 2014 and 2022, yielded 186, 148 and 97 articles, respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Sample of news articles

A smaller sample of articles was selected to be subjected to quantitative content analysis: 90 articles of Público, 100 articles of El País and 100 articles of Guardian. The coding grid was based on the literature review (e.g. Dudo et al. 2011, Kojo and Innola 2017) and on previous work regarding media representations of emerging technologies (Delicado et al. 2016) and focused on the characteristics of the articles, on the actors mentioned, the coverage of domestic IoT, risks and benefits.

The full sample was subjected to a qualitative analysis, using the software MaxQda, that focused particularly on sociotechnical imaginaries (Task 2 of the project), and was used also to map the network of actors involved in IoT (Task 1 of the project). Those results are not included in this report.

Media coverage of IoT

Overall, it could be said that the media coverage of IoT is not particularly intense. Less than one hundred articles were found in the main quality daily newspaper in Portugal. A few more were found in El País and The Guardian, but these newspapers have specialised technology sections.

The evolution over time seems to show a declining interest in IoT from 2020 onwards (Figure 2). Peak coverage was reached in 2025 in The Guardian, in 2017 in El País and in 2018 in Público. In the later, the number of articles was usually higher at the time of the Web Summit (November), held in Lisbon since 2016, where new products were launched and debates on digital topics took place.

Figure 2 News articles on IoT by newspaper and year of publication

Regarding the type of articles where IoT is mentioned (Figure 3), it is noticeable the prevalence of short articles, particularly in El País and The Guardian, whereas in Público opinion pieces (mostly by researchers and company representatives) have an almost similar weight. Therefore, it can be assumed that media coverage of IoT is fairly limited.

Figure 3 News articles on IoT by newspaper and type of article

This is particularly true in the case of Público, since the majority of articles that mention IoT do not have it as their central theme (Figure 4). IoT is mentioned mostly alongside other digital technologies, such as 5G, virtual reality, cloud computing, artificial intelligence. Conversely, close to 80% of articles in El País and about half in The Guardian address IoT as the main topic.

Figure 4 News articles on IoT by newspaper and whether IoT is the central theme

Figure 5 Social actors mentioned in the news articles by newspaper

Although we did not succeed in coding the articles by themes, the kind of social actors mentioned in the articles give us some clues on the content of articles (Figure 5). By far the most frequently mentioned actors in all three newspapers are companies. That is hardly surprising, since IoT mostly concerns consumer products and news articles are often centred on publicising new products, under development and show in trade fairs or already in the market. Research actors (research centres, universities, individual researchers) are also often featured, particularly in The Guardian. Government agencies feature more prominently in the Guardian and El País and international organisations (such as the United Nations or the European Commission) are more frequently mentioned in Público. Civil society organisations are only mentioned in The Guardian and El País.

Domestic IoT

Not all IoT applications are used in domestic settings. In fact, IoT has a variety of domains of application: industry, farming, smart cities, smart grids, environmental monitoring, etc.

Regarding media coverage of the topic, more than half of articles in Público do not mention at all domestic applications of IoT (Figure 6). That proportion is reverted in El País and particularly in The Guardian, where only a minority of articles do not mention domestic IoT.

Figure 6 News articles on IoT by newspaper and whether domestic IoT is mentioned

Thus, when analysing the kind of domestic IoT devices mentioned in the articles (Figure 7), only a few are found in Público: connected cars (8 articles), televisions (5) and clothes (5). In El País the most frequently mentioned devices are again cars (27 articles), heating and air conditioning (19), video cameras (9) and fridges (12). In The Guardian, cars (30 articles) are again at the top of the list, followed by heating and air conditioning (27), fridges (20), video cameras (17), smart lighting (16), smart watches (16) and voice assistants (16).

Figure 7 Domestic IoT devices mentioned in the news articles by newspaper

Risks and benefits of IoT

As with any new technology, the debates are often focused on the benefits and affordances they bring but also on the downsides and risks. An analysis of the tone of each article (Figure8) led us to ascertain that close to half the articles in El País are positive (focusing on the benefits of IoT), whereas that proportion is much lower in The Guardian, where negative articles are more frequent than in the other newspapers. Neutral articles, that are merely descriptive and do not take any stance on the technology, are more common in El País, whereas balanced articles (that provide both positive and negative valuations) are more frequent in The Guardian and Público.

Figure 8 News articles on IoT by newspaper and tone of the article

In much the same line, the majority of articles in The Guardian mention risks, whereas in Público this proportion does down to slightly less than half and in El País to less than a third (Figure 9).

Figure 9 News articles on IoT by newspaper and whether IoT risk are mentioned

Regarding the types of risks that are mentioned in the news articles, several are recurrently mentioned:

- Privacy invasion: “Thanks to IoT, more devices than ever are listening to us, monitoring us, tracking us, recording us – even if it’s not always clear what they should be allowed to listen to, how much they should be allowed to monitor and track and what their recording limits ought to be” (The Guardian, 2015)
- Cyberattacks “Internet of Things (IoT) botnets are cross-systems of connected devices with security flaws - such as webcams and video recorders - that, after being attacked by malware, are controlled by a single attacker.” (El País, 2018)
- Cyberkinetic attacks: “Beyond hacked kettles and fridges, ‘internet of things’ devices, such as driverless cars, can present alarmingly real security threats that could be incredibly dangerous if the right security isn’t in place” (The Guardian, 2017)
- Data misuse: “Targeting and segmenting populations into workable demographics is now considered a necessary way of identifying potential buyers, yet it leads marketers to think of customers as disembodied data rather than individuals” (The Guardian, 2015)
- increasing the digital divide: “There is still a high rate of people who don't have a smartphone, or who don't have a mid-range or top-of-the-range handset. For this world of the Internet of Things to work, it can't work with a low-end mobile phone” (Público, 2016)

On the other hand, the benefits of IoT are mentioned in around half the articles in Público, a little more than that in El País and a little less in The Guardian (Figure 10).

Figure 10 News articles on IoT by newspaper and whether IoT benefits are mentioned

As to the types of benefits that are mentioned, a few stand out:

- convenience: “the so-called internet of things promises consumers increased convenience – the remotely operated thermostat ... is a leading example” (The Guardian, 2016)
- safety: “its robot vacuum cleaner, recently launched in Spain, video monitors your home while it cleans, avoiding obstacles at the same time, and whose images can be viewed from your mobile phone with the Smart ThinQ app. If it detects any movement, it alerts you” (El País, 2017)
- efficiency: “Bins, toasters, washing machines and lights will be able to talk to each other for automatic, more efficient control and monitoring (The Guardian, 2016)
- customisation: “The analysis, management and exploitation of data linked to IoT will create new markets, products and services under more accurate patterns in detecting consumer tastes, needs and preferences” (El País, 2018)
- health improvements: “The health data that can be easily collected in digital format is manifold, and the way in which technology can improve our health is also multi-layered. Firstly, the centralisation of data allows our medical history to be immediately accessible if, for example, we arrive at an emergency department unconscious. This data can include drug allergies, vaccination reports, tests or even the sequence of our genome. Secondly, there is great potential for the use of sensors, whether fixed (such as cameras), portable (such as mobile phones) or "wearable" (such as smart watches), which measure a multitude of signals, from the number of steps we take to the rhythm of our heart” (Público, 2019)

Finally, in an exercise to understand the key ideas in the news articles. we built word clouds based on the titles of the news articles for each newspaper. In the case of Público (Figure 11), the words more often repeated, besides internet and things, are opinion (referring to the type of article), future, companies, cybersecurity, intelligence, and smart. In El País (Figure 12), the most common words are country, companies, Telefonica (the main telecommunications operator), technology, Vodafone (another company), future, connected, business, and Spain. In the case of The Guardian, the most frequent words are smart, Amazon, home, Google, tech/technology, new, Echo, data, Nest, review and network.

